

An overview of the trends, obstacles, and future directions in AI-Based Teaching and Learning Systems

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative and supportive technique for enhancing teaching and learning experiences. This research study aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the existing AI-based teaching and learning systems. Through a comprehensive search in major academic databases, a diverse set of articles were selected and examined. The research explores various AI techniques employed in educational contexts, their applications, benefits, challenges, and future directions. The findings contribute to in-depth knowledge of the current state of AI-based teaching and learning systems, shedding light on potential advancements and areas requiring further research.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Learning, Teaching, Techniques

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Research Back ground: The revolutionize educational system shaking hands by incorporating AI into teaching and learning systems, educational environments will be more inclusive, efficient, and adaptive, meeting each student's unique needs and preparing for the future needs. AI makes it easier for students and educators throughout the world to collaborate and communicate. A more international approach to education can be promoted by connecting students from various origins and cultures using online platforms with AI-driven features. Administrative operations like data analysis, assessment, and grading can be automated by AI. This frees up teacher's time from repetitive chores and enables them to enrich more on instructing and giving each student individualized support. With the help of AI technologies, teachers may give pupils immediate feedback on their work, where improvements need to make. An approach to learning that is more iterative and self-directed is encouraged by this ongoing assessment. We can make with interactive and captivating learning resources, such instructional games, simulations, and virtual reality experiences. AI can be modified to help kids who require specific needs by providing personalized assistance.

Objectives: The objectives of the research study are,

- To analyze existing AI-based teaching and learning systems.
- To identify current trends, the benefits and challenges, and propose future directions.

Methodology: A systematic approach was followed, including a comprehensive search strategy, article selection criteria, data extraction, and thematic analysis. The structured questionnaire prepared to analyze the challenges and impact of AI in teaching and learning. The responses of 247 were collected from students and teachers of educational institutions and the sample respondents were selected by adopting judgmental sampling method was adopted. For analysis purpose the simple statistical tools were used.

Review of Literature:

- (BAÍDOO-ANU & OWUSU ANSAH, 2023), This is an exploratory study that synthesizes recent available literature to present some potential advantages and disadvantages of ChatGPT in promoting teaching and learning. The study provides recommendations on how to leverage ChatGPT to maximize teaching and learning. Policymakers, researchers, educators, and technical experts can work together and start the conversation about how to use these emerging general AI tools safely and constructive to improve education and support student learning.
- (Chan, 2023), this research article pictured that higher educational institutions by the implications of text-generating AI technology. Based on these findings, the study proposes the multifaceted impacts of integrating AI into academics. The study had three dimensions: Education, Administration and Operations. The education aspect focuses on using AI to improve educational outcomes, addresses issues related to privacy and security. The operational aspect addresses issues related to infrastructure and training.
- (Sanusi et al., 2022), Despite ongoing discussions and growing research in this emerging field, educators' perceptions of machine learning remain understudied. By describing the initial conceptions of machine learning teaching among practicing teachers in Africa. The study stated that educators should be play a part in the process of co-designing resources and, importantly, curriculum factors to integrate machine learning into mainstream education. Involving teachers in the development process helps contextualize machine learning, thereby contributing to real-world impact and social change.
- (Kong, 2020), this article attempts to develop strategies for using AI in art education. To this end, the authors examined the current status of the application of AI in art education and summarized the problems of these applications. Next, the promoting role of AI in art teaching was analyzed in detail, and three strategies were developed to promote the applications of AI in modern art teaching, and the proposed model can quantify the impact of using AI in art education and has good application potential.

AI Techniques in Teaching and Learning Systems: AI paves a path in revolutionizing teaching and learning systems, ushering in a digital era of personalized and efficient education. These technologies harness the power of machine learning - (ML) algorithms allow AI systems to analyze data, make predictions, and adapt to learners' needs, enabling personalized learning experiences, natural language processing - (NLP) techniques enable to understand human language, also facilitating communication between learners and AI systems, Deep Learning - (DL) models, such as neural networks, enable AI systems to extract complex patterns, enhancing tasks like speech recognition, image analysis, and natural language understanding, Intelligent Tutoring Systems - (ITS) utilize AI to provide personalized instruction, adapt to learners' progress, and offer feedback, simulating the guidance of human tutors, Recommender Systems – (RS) to suggest relevant learning resources, fostering personalized and adaptive learning, Virtual Reality - (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies, combined with AI, create immersive and interactive learning environments that enhance engagement and comprehension, Data Mining and Analytics enable educators to extract insights, identify learning patterns, and make data-driven decisions and data analytics to tailor educational experiences to individual needs.

Adaptive learning platforms use AI algorithms to assess students' strengths and weaknesses, allowing for customized learning paths that address specific areas of improvement. Virtual tutors powered by AI engage students in interactive and dynamic ways, providing real-time feedback and adapting teaching strategies based on individual progress. Additionally, AI facilitates the development of intelligent educational content, like smart textbooks and immersive simulations, enriching the learning experience. Through predictive analytics, AI can forecast student performance trends, enabling educators to intervene early and offer targeted support.

Applications of AI in Teaching and Learning: The applications of AI in teaching and learning have transformed traditional education paradigms, ushering in a wave of innovation that enhances the overall learning experience. Personalized Learning AI facilitates adaptive learning pathways tailored to individual learners' needs, preferences, and abilities. Intelligent tutoring systems, powered by AI algorithms, provide personalized learning paths by analyzing individual student performance and adapting instructional strategies accordingly. AI-based educational content creation tools generate dynamic and engaging materials, from interactive simulations to customized assessments, catering to diverse learning styles.

Automated Assessment and Feedback AI automates the assessment process, providing timely and constructive feedback to learners, reducing teachers' workload. Virtual assistants and chatbots leverage the processing of natural language to assist students in real-time, answering queries, providing feedback, and fostering a more interactive learning environment. Classroom Management and Support AI systems support teachers in tasks like student monitoring, behavior analysis, and early identification of at-risk students. Educational Gamification AI-powered gamification enhances motivation, engagement, and knowledge retention through game-like elements and adaptive challenges. Furthermore, AI facilitates the development of virtual and augmented reality applications, offering immersive learning experiences that transcend traditional classroom boundaries. As these applications continue to evolve, the inclusion of AI in teaching and learning not only enhances efficiency but also promotes a more adaptive, student-centric approach to education.

Benefits and Challenges of AI-Based Teaching and Learning Systems: AI-based teaching and learning systems offer a plethora of benefits that significantly enhance the educational landscape. The key advantages of AI can tailor learning experiences to needs of individual students, understanding content and stepping to optimize comprehension and engagement. The efficiency of educational processes is greatly improved through automation, freeing up educators' time for more personalized interactions with students. Efficient Feedback and Assessment Automated feedback and assessment save time, enable immediate responses, and provide personalized guidance. Increased Access to Education AI facilitates remote and flexible learning opportunities, bridging geographical and socioeconomic gaps. Additionally, the inclusivity of AI-based systems accommodates various learning platforms, ensuring that education is accessible and adaptable to a wide range of students. In essence, the benefits of AI in teaching and learning systems extend beyond efficiency gains, fostering a more tailored, engaging, and equitable educational experience.

When discussed about the challenges, one significant concern is the potential for bias in algorithms, as AI systems might inadvertently perpetuate or exacerbate existing inequalities in education. Ensuring the fairness and impartiality of these systems requires continuous monitoring and refinement. Another challenge lies in the infrastructural investments and staff training, which may pose barriers for some educational institutions. Additionally, the reliance on technology in education raises concerns on data security and privacy, especially when handling sensitive student

information. The dynamic nature of technology may also outpace the ability of educators to adapt, leading to a potential digital divide. Moreover, the depersonalization of the learning experience, if not carefully managed, could hinder the development of crucial interpersonal skills.

Current Trends in AI-Based Teaching and Learning Systems: The current trends widely applied in educational institutions are integrating AI into Learning Management System enhances administrative tasks, personalization, analytics, and learner support. Next, Chatbots and Virtual Assistants provide immediate support, answer queries, and engage in conversational learning and Natural Language Processing for Essay Evaluation, and timely feedback to learners. Then the Intelligent Tutoring Systems support learners in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) domains, fostering deeper understanding and problem-solving skills. Gamification and Game-Based Learning with AI create immersive, adaptive, and engaging experiences, promoting active learning.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION:

Benefits in implementing AI based teaching and learning systems: The Pearson Correlation was used to analyze the relationship between the respondent's benefits towards AI Techniques related factors during their teaching and learning systems.

Table: 1 – Benefits of AI in Teaching and Learning systems

H ₀₁ – Significantly no relationship between the benefits of using AI techniques in Teaching and Learning systems					
Factors		Personalized learning experiences	Improved efficiency of educational processes	Identifying and addressing individual learning needs	Enhanced student engagement
Personalized learning experiences	Pearson Correlation	1	.925**	.834**	.819**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
Improved efficiency of educational processes	Pearson Correlation		1	.898**	.876**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.000

Identifying and addressing individual learning needs	Pearson Correlation			1	.862**
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.000
Enhanced student engagement	Pearson Correlation				1
	Sig. (2-tailed)				

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The value of r is significant at a level less than the 0.01 set as the criteria for statistical significance, there is a positive correlation between the benefits of using AI techniques in efficient improvised educational processes ($r=0.925$, $N=247$, $p=0.000$). There is a positive correlation among identifying and addressing individual training needs ($r =0.834$) and positive correlation with enhanced and active student engagement ($r= 0.819$). From the analysis, there is positive relation between improved educational processes, identifying learning needs and enhanced student engagement ($r=0.898$, 0.876 , 0.862). It is inferred that the respondents have enough knowledge to complete perform happily and accepts the AI techniques even though facing difficulties in using AI in teaching and learning systems.

Challenges in implementing AI based teaching and learning systems based on Age:

Table: 2 – Challenges – Age - Performance and Learning needs

H ₀₂ – Age does not influence the usage of AI techniques in the academic performance and learning readiness in Teaching and Learning systems						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Enhanced overall academic performance	Between Groups	154.556	2	77.278	654.413	.000
	Within Groups	28.813	244	.118		
	Total	183.370	246			
Learning readiness	Between Groups	163.744	2	81.872	532.113	.000
	Within Groups	37.542	244	.154		
	Total	201.287	246			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The p value of academic performance and learning needs of AI techniques in teaching and learning systems are less than the significance level (5%), hence null hypothesis rejected, states that there is a significant difference between these variables and age of the respondents.

Post Hoc - Tukey HSD Test

Dependent Variable	Age	Age	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.
Enhanced overall academic performance	21-30 Yrs	31-40 Yrs	2.08631 [*]	.06205	.000
		41-50 Yrs	1.12912 [*]	.05572	.000
	31-40 Yrs	21-30 Yrs	-2.08631 [*]	.06205	.000
		41-50 Yrs	-.95719 [*]	.07395	.000
	41-50 Yrs	21-30 Yrs	-1.12912 [*]	.05572	.000
		31-40 Yrs	.95719 [*]	.07395	.000
Learning readiness	21-30 Yrs	31-40 Yrs	2.09473 [*]	.07083	.000
		41-50 Yrs	1.25929 [*]	.06360	.000
	31-40 Yrs	21-30 Yrs	-2.09473 [*]	.07083	.000
		41-50 Yrs	-.83544 [*]	.08442	.000
	41-50 Yrs	21-30 Yrs	-1.25929 [*]	.06360	.000
		31-40 Yrs	.83544 [*]	.08442	.000

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Post Hoc -Tukey HSD test is used to test the significant difference between the group based on mean difference at the 0.05 level. The above table exhibits that having enhanced academic performance with AI techniques is the challenging one for the employees above 30 years than youngsters. And based on high mean difference for the learning readiness effect rate is high with the 21 to 30 years' age group employees than those above 30 years.

Suggestions: The researchers' aim is to understand how well the usage of various AI techniques supports the teaching and learning systems. The educators and learners are having the opportunity to choose their own AI tool — as long as they required knowledge to handle the technique implemented in their institution. Every educational institution should realize crucial need of hour of using AI tools with well balance training system for both educators and learners, though it's a cost effective one. Implementing latest technologies and algorithms of AI would cause challenges on both the ends but possible with the learning and updating the AI techniques. In deciding to

facilitate the enriched learning platforms educational institutions can choose from a wide array of AI options might also help in betterment of organizational survival on long run.

Future Directions and Research Challenges: Explainable AI in Education Developing transparent AI models and systems that provide explanations for their decision-making processes. Collaborative AI Systems for Group Learning AI systems supporting collaborative learning, fostering cooperation, communication, and collective intelligence. Ethical Guidelines and Frameworks for AI in Education Establishing ethical frameworks and guidelines to ensure learner privacy, data security, and address algorithmic bias. Integrating AI into Teachers' Educational Programs and Preparing educators to effectively utilize AI technologies, leveraging its potential for instructional design, assessment, and personalized instruction. AI-Based Assessment and Credentialing Exploring AI's potential in authentic assessment, digital badges, and micro-credentials to recognize learners' competencies and achievements.

Conclusion: The wide understanding of the current state of research in AI techniques, applications, benefits, challenges, current trends, and future directions in AI-based teaching and learning systems. Implications for Practice Educators and policymakers can inculcate the inputs of this study to enhance instructional practices, integrate AI technologies effectively, and address associated challenges. Furthermore, the recommendations for further exploration on addressing ethical concerns, developing explainable AI models, and optimizing educational systems by integrating AI in various contexts to maximize its potential benefits.

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